

Stručni rad

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PRIKAZ TEHNIČKIH PRAVILA UTVSI – DVGW UTVSI DVGW informacija o vodi 80

**Zaštita objekata sistema za snabdevanje vodom – Vodič za
izradu koncepta zaštite objekata**

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Rezime

U Republici Srbiji je primetan nedostatak nacionalnih tehničkih pravila i propisa u oblasti voda. Opređeljeno da dopuni i inovira tehničke standarde, UTVSI saraduje sa nemačkim stručnim udruženjima: DVGW u oblasti snabdevanja vodom od 2008, i DWA u oblasti odvođenja i prečišćavanja otpadnih voda od 2012. U ovom radu dat je prikaz UTVSI DVGW informacije o vodi 80 „Zaštita objekata sistema za snabdevanje vodom – Vodič za izradu koncepta zaštite objekata“, koji omogućuje procenu rizika i sprovođenje mera zaštite objekata sistema za snabdevanje vodom. Informacija dopunjuje tehničko uputstvo UTVSI DVGW W 1050 (M) “Zaštita objekata sistema za snabdevanje vodom” i predstavlja podršku za razvoj koncepta zaštite objekata.

Ključne reči: tehnička pravila, zaštita objekata, procena rizika, sprovođenje mera zaštite objekata

REVIEW OF TECHNICAL RULES UTVSI - DVGW UTVSI DVGW water information 80

**Protection of water supply system facilities – Guide for
developing a concept for the protection of facilities**

Summary

In the Republic of Serbia, there is a noticeable lack of national technical rules and regulations in the field of water. Determined to supplement and innovate technical standards, UTVSI cooperates with German professional associations: DVGW in the field of water supply since 2008, and DWA in the field of waste water drainage and treatment since 2012. This paper presents the UTVSI DVGW information on water 80, “Protection of facilities of the water supply system - Guide for the development of the concept of protection of facilities”, which enables risk assessment and the implementation of measures to protect the facilities of the water supply system. complements the technical instruction UTVSI DVGW W 1050 (M) “Protection of water supply system facilities” and represents support for the development of the concept of facility protection.

Keywords: technical rules, building protection, risk assessment, implementation of building protection measures